

Studying TV-shows with network analysis: the *small world* of Breaking Bad

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Abstract

Network theory has been used to analyse literary works by means of representing fictional characters and their relations as nodes connected by edges in a graph. In this report we analyse a social network representing the plot of “Breaking Bad”, the famous tv-show, by looking at its features and how they evolve with time. What we aim to illustrate is a new way of looking at narrative structures with a reproducible case-study on how to apply network measurements on literary plots to analyse their features.

Context

There is no doubt that quantitative sciences have revolutionized the Humanities, by offering new tools and methods to approach human artifacts in unexpected ways. As an example, it is well known how statistical measurements had an impact on the analysis of literary works, with the rising of new disciplines such as Text Mining and Corpus Linguistics. However, among recent advances in quantitative methods applied to the humanities, we should of course include network theory. Network theory is a discipline that aims to analyse relations among different actors by representing their interactions as edges that connect nodes in a graph. There are several fields in which network theory is applied: from computer science to biology, from physics to engineering, from bibliometrics to literary studies. In all these domains the analysis of networks has demonstrated some general mechanisms by which the interactions among multiple entities are regulated.

Of course, the analysis of literary plots has been one of the major fields in which network theory has been applied to literary studies: due to their nature, fictional stories can be easily represented into a graph where characters interact with each other by means of edges that connect their respective nodes. One of the research groups that first carried out this idea was the Stanford Literary Lab, led by Franco Moretti. In one of their pamphlets, “Network Theory, Plot Analysis”, Franco Moretti states: «A network is made of vertices and edges; a plot, of characters and actions: characters will be the vertices of the network, interactions the edges, [...] two characters are linked if some words have passed between them: an interaction, is a speech act » [1]. However, there are many ways to represent a network of a fictional story: two characters may interact if they speak in the same scene, even if they do not address each other, or if they are co-mentioned by the storyteller in the same scene. Although, after this operation of abstraction, what you are studying is not the literary artifact itself but a model that offers a way of interpreting it by means of its reduced representation. Still quoting Moretti, «once you make a network of a play, you stop working on the play proper, and work on a model instead: you reduce the text to characters and interactions, abstract them from everything else, and this

process of reduction and abstraction makes the model obviously much less than the original object [...] – but also, in another sense, much more than it» [1].

Problem and Motivation

In this report we want to examine how network theory can be furtherly used in the analysis of fictional plots, by applying network measurements to a graph extracted from the plot of the famous tv-show *Breaking Bad* (Vince Gilligan, 2008). What we want to address, with this type of research, are the following questions:

- Is the network of a plot characterised by certain properties that might determine its structure? Do these properties change as the network evolves in time?
- Can the importance of fictional characters somehow be related to the position of a node in a network?

The first question goes with the analysis of how nodes are connected and the way those connections are distributed. With respect to our research, we would like to see if the network structure can coincide with that of a *small-world* network, a concept first defined in network theory by Watts and Strogatz in 1998 [2]. A small-world graph, by analogy with the small-world phenomenon (popularly known as *six degrees of separation*), is a graph in which most of the nodes are not neighbours of each other; however, they are likely to share at least one neighbour and most nodes can be reached by any other node with a small number of steps. In scientific terms, «these systems can be highly clustered [...], yet have small characteristic path lengths, like random graphs» [2]. In this type of networks, usually, we have an over-abundance of *hubs* – nodes in the network with a high *degree*. The degree of a node is its number of edges. Through these hubs that are hugely connected, nodes with a relatively small degree can be connected to any other node with a short path.

The purpose of this analysis is to demonstrate that fictional plots might be represented with strongly tied networks that show asymmetries in the distribution of edges. This type of networks, like small-worlds or *scale-free* networks [3], are typical of many systems in biology, physics and social sciences. These networks are studied because they model many real-world systems, like neuron cells, protein systems or voters' networks. For clear reasons, it is extremely interesting for literary studies to discover that fictional plots might be modelled with networks that already have applications in real-world situations. The presence of small-world phenomena regulating fictional stories might suggest a resemblance between narrative and real-world situations, thus supporting the Aristotelian theory that every fiction is a *mimesis* of reality.

Moreover, small-world networks have demonstrated to be more robust than random graphs, meaning that their structure is more resilient to perturbations [4]. Consequently, what we want to furtherly investigate is that, if the property of small-worldness is given in our characters' network, it should not disappear due to the deletions of certain nodes. We will follow the evolution of the plot to change the structure of the graph. In the end, we would like to verify that, if the network of *Breaking Bad* manifests the small-world property, this type of property does not disappear as the graph evolves in time across the 5 seasons of the tv-show.

After this network-level analysis, we would like to focus on one of the aforementioned features of the nodes, their degree, to see if it is somehow related to the fictional role that a character covers along the story. In order to do so, we want to compare the result of different centrality measurements applied to the nodes: the degree centrality, the eigenvector centrality and the betweenness centrality. These three measurements exploit different types of information about nodes and their edges to understand their importance in the network. We want to test if these types of measures might be able to reflect the importance of fictional roles: moreover, we want to see if the different importance of a character, with respect to the centrality measure applied, might be conditioned by the specific actions that the character undertakes in the story and by the relations that it holds with other characters.

Datasets

The social network of Breaking Bad is the result of a text-mining process carried by Francesco Bailo [5] on the Wiki page of Breaking Bad [6]. The graph was built based on textual copresence of two characters in the same scene. In order to do so, each paragraph of the episode synopsis on the website was text-mined for instance of character names: if two characters were mentioned in the same paragraph, then an edge was drawn among the two, with a weight based on the number of contexts they share together.

The dataset has been made freely available by the author in JSON format. We decided to conduct our analysis by using the Python library *NetworkX*, a package designed for conducting analysis on complex networks. Moreover, for applying further statistical analysis we exploited another Python library: *powerlaw*, used for the analysis and comparison of fat-tailed distributions.

The dataset consists in an undirected weighted graph with 131 nodes and 969 edges. The nodes were identified by integers (*ids*) and labelled with character names. The edges were labelled with a weight attribute corresponding to the number of contexts shared together by two character instances.

Figure 1: the social network of Breaking Bad

Validity and Reliability

This dataset, as mentioned earlier, is the result of a data-mining process on `breakingbad.wikia.com`. What we are manipulating can be conceived as a matrix of co-occurrence of character instances (e.g. names) extracted from textual paragraphs of episode synopsis. Therefore, we need to acknowledge that our model is built on multiple abstraction processes. The story of Breaking Bad was, indeed, summarized in textual format and then the text was mined in order to get structured information.

There is no doubt that the text-mining process, an automatic one, could have damaged the reliability of characters' connections in the graph: in fact, it is enough that two characters are mentioned in the same paragraph, even though they are not present in the same scene, to be tied together. By the way, the result of the web-scraping algorithm, in general, seems consistent in tracking the presence of characters in a scene and able, also, to handle noisy text.

Moreover, the number of contexts shared together by two characters, even if it is not able to accurately represent the physical copresence of two characters in a scene, is surely an index of how much two names are semantically related across a text and thus a possible representation of the weight of the bound between two entities. Overall, we feel confident to conclude that the graph extracted from `breakingbad.wikia.com` is still valid to conduct a network analysis on the plot of the tv-show.

Measures

For analysing if our network is a small-world, we want to compute its small world coefficient σ . As we stated before, a small-world network is a network characterized both by high clustering and small path lengths. The small-world coefficient is a measure that compares the clustering coefficient and the average path length of a considered network with those of an equivalent random network. It is described by the formula:

$$\sigma = \frac{\frac{C}{C_r}}{\frac{L}{L_r}}$$

Where C is the clustering coefficient, L the average path length, and C_r and L_r the clustering coefficient and the path length of an equal random graph. If $\sigma > 1$ then the considered graph is a small-world.

Small-world networks, as already said, are often related to fat-tailed distributions of degrees. We already mentioned how small worlds tend to have their properties due to a high number of *hubs* (nodes with high degree) that connect distant nodes in small steps. A fat-tailed distribution is a distribution that exhibits large *skewness*, meaning an asymmetry between the values of the distribution and their mean. Networks where many nodes have very large degree tend to have many values in the so-called tail, and thus to fit a fat-tailed distribution. These networks are also more tightly connected than others where edges are normally distributed.

Fat-tailed distributions include many types of distributions: the power law distribution, the log-normal distribution and the stretched exponential distribution, among others. Power laws are often studied in network theory since they are index of network invariance to scale and preferential attachment to hubs [3]. However, the study of Clauset et al. [7] has demonstrated

that scale-free networks are in fact very rare in nature and their degree distribution can often be better modelled with other types of distributions, such as the log-normal distribution or power laws with an exponential cut-off for large values.

Therefore, we intend to examine the distribution of degrees of our network by comparing different distribution models to explain the data with a likelihood ratio test. In short, a likelihood ratio test is a test that serves to compare different distribution models and state which is the most plausible for explaining the data [8]. Once we have examined our distribution of degrees and have observed many values in the tail, we can compare different types of distributions and see which fits better.

We already stated that a crucial factor for small-world networks is their robustness. To demonstrate the resilience of the network, we consider sufficient that the small-world coefficient σ should not drop to values < 1 after several perturbations of the network. In order to verify it, we are going to mimic the evolution of characters' relations in time by adding an imaginary orthogonal axis T to our graph, representing time, and 5 additional planes t_n devoted to each season of the TV-show, where the graph will be modified by deleting nodes corresponding to the characters that die for season.

In order to tackle our second problem, related to the usefulness of centrality measures with respect to fictional characters importance, we intend to apply three different measures of centrality: the degree centrality, the eigenvector centrality and the betweenness centrality. The degree centrality of a node is merely based on the degree, the number of edges incident to that node. The eigenvector centrality, instead, calculates the importance of a node by considering its connections with nodes that are themselves important. To do so, in the eigenvector centrality, the relation of a node to high-scoring nodes contributes more to the score of a node than connections to low-scoring nodes [9]. Finally, in short, the betweenness centrality measures how many times a node (e.g. a character) acts as a bridge along the shortest path between two other nodes [10].

We expect to see that the main characters of the series figure as the most central nodes. Moreover, we would like to compare how different centrality measures might highlight different types of role that a character undertakes in the story.

Results

The small-world coefficient was computed by randomly generating 10 equivalent random networks with approximately 10 rewiring per edge with the NetworkX algorithm *nx.small-world.sigma*. The measurements confirmed our hypothesis, with a small-world coefficient of approximately 1.1156.

In addition, after plotting the cumulative frequency distribution of our degrees in logarithmic scale and after performing different likelihood ratio tests, we are confident to state that the degree distribution in the network of Breaking Bad can be modelled with a truncated power-law (a power law with an exponential cut-off for large values).

Figure 2: Cumulative distribution function of the degrees in logarithmic scale. In black, the distribution of degrees of the network. The red dotted line is the power-law distribution and the blue dotted line is the power-law with an exponential cut-off.

Comparison	Result (likelihood, <i>p</i> value)
Power law vs. Log-Normal	-1.35, 0.17
Power law vs. Power law with cut-off	-1.88, 0.02
Power law vs. Stretched Exponential	-1.44, 0.15

Table 1: Results of likelihood tests for the comparison of different fat-tailed distributions. Negative likelihood values mean that the second distribution is preferred over the first.

This is a fundamental point because leads us to suggest that the interactions among characters in fictional plots creates highly clustered networks, and these networks present big hubs that connect distant characters in a small number of steps. Moreover, as our degree distribution suggests, this type of networks may present scale-free behaviours for certain portions of the nodes. All these conclusions were previously demonstrated by other studies. Stiller et al. [11] demonstrated that a small-world network appeared from modelling the relations of ten of Shakespeare's plays. Another research, led by Amelia C. Sparavigna [12], inferred a power law, and thus a scale-free structure, in the network of the first novel of *Harry Potter*. Moreover, a research conducted by Alberich and Rossello [13] demonstrated a truncated power-law distribution for a study concerning the collaborations among characters in the Marvel Universe. All this studies, included this one, support the hypothesis that one of the intrinsic properties of fictional structures is to mimic real-world situations, thus embracing the Aristotelian view of imitation as the basic theoretical principle in artistic creation.

With respect to the evolution in time of our graph, the small-world coefficient remained > 1 for all the time-windows t_n , even if some characters with very high degree were deleted (like Gustavo Fring in the fourth season and Walter White in the fifth). Interestingly, except for t_1 , as the number of nodes diminished the small-world coefficient increased. Overall, these measures allow us to say that the network of Breaking Bad is very robust and that the small-world structure is preserved even though the network receives relevant perturbations.

Moreover, following our results, we can suggest that the robustness of a network might be a relevant feature in the development of fictional stories: the fact that the distance among characters do not get too high as the network is modified in time, might be comparable to how characters can still make a story to pursue even after dramatic events.

Time window	σ
T0	1.115577
T1	1.115467
T2	1.122584
T3	1.123780
T4	1.145699
T5	1.274601

Table 2: Small-world coefficients for different time-windows of the graph. T0 corresponds to the original graph, where all the characters are present, T5 corresponds to the graph of the characters still alive after the last season of the show.

In the following table are reported the first ten characters, sorted by decreasing importance, and their respective value, for all the three measures of centrality.

	Degree centrality	Eigenvector centrality	Betweenness centrality
1	Walter White, 1905	Walter White, 0.55612	Hector Salamanca, 0.20576
2	Jesse Pinkman, 1318	Jesse Pinkman, 0.42708	Jesse Pinkman, 0.11704
3	Hector Salamanca, 1261	Hector Salamanca, 0.4142	Walter White, 0.08270
4	Hank Schrader, 891	Skyler White, 0.30956	Mike Ehrmantraut, 0.08146
5	Skyler White, 816	Hank Schrader, 0.28932	Hank Schrader, 0.06061
6	Gustavo Fring, 481	Gustavo Fring, 0.17412	Gustavo Fring, 0.05687
7	Mike Ehrmantraut, 391	Marie Schrader, 0.15224	Skyler White, 0.053336
8	Marie Schrader, 388	Mike Ehrmantraut, 0.1461	Steven Gomez, 0.04929
9	Walter White Jr., 329	Walter White, Jr. 0.13885	Saul Goodman, 0.04214
10	Saul Goodman, 325	Saul Goodman, 0.1292	Skinny Pete, 0.03900

Table 3: ten most important characters, sorted by centrality measure.

The values found do not disattend our expectations, with the most important characters of the show figuring as the most central nodes for all three measures. However, it is pretty interesting to notice how the rank changes, with respect to the type of centrality measurements: if both degree and eigenvector centralities have Walter White (the protagonist) as the best scoring character, the results of the betweenness centrality say that Hector Salamanca, one of the drug

lords in the story, has the highest score and side characters such as Skinny Pete figure in the ten most central characters.

Since we cannot directly compare different centralities, at the end, our assertion will be qualitative. Following our results, if the first two centrality measures, the first based on the degree and the second on the eigenvector, seem to reflect the fictional importance of characters in almost the same way, the eigenvector centrality seems more appropriate in highlighting what type of characters have more importance in the narrative. It is the case of Skyler White, wife of the protagonist, that with the eigenvector centrality scores as the fourth most important character, presumably due to its relationship with Walter White and the whole White family.

The betweenness centrality, instead, is the one whose results deviates the most from the other two measures. The importance that the measure gives to side-characters might suggest that, if we consider the entire web of relations, this type of fictional characters (such as Skinny Pete or Hector Salamanca) might be more important than main characters in connecting different portions of the network. This is an interesting discovery and deserves more investigation, to finally state if the results might be due to the features of our network or to the intrinsic properties of this fictional characters.

Critique

Even though we consider the results of our research relevant for the study of networks representing literary works, more specifically fictional works, we could not exempt us from taking in considerations few critiques to our work.

First, the fact that the network was extracted from a textual synopsis and not from the tv-show itself. We already tackled this question when we dealt with the validity and reliability of our data. As said before, the number of textual copresences of two character instances does not adequately model the relations among two characters in a story, just the semantic bound between two entities in a text. This might be misleading when trying to generalise relational properties of a network, when its connections are not an effective representation of how two instances interact. Nonetheless, the results of our study show that the network is able to reflect the narrative importance of different characters in the fiction and, in addition, the features that our graph presents are similar to others already encountered in the literature.

Secondly, there are several measures that offer an index of the small-worldness of a network. The small-world coefficient σ , even though it is pretty common, it's influenced by network's size [14]. Therefore, it would have been better to use different type of measures, like the small world measure ω or the Small World Index (SWI).

A final remark can be made, related to the application of centrality measures to analyse the importance of fictional characters. In fact, it is difficult to generalise a relation between the centrality of a node and the fictional role of a character, because it implies qualitative judgments on what we consider important in the influence that a character has in the story. However, further applications of centrality measures on fictional networks can give more insights on this issue and provide useful methodologies of investigation.

References

1. F. Moretti, Network theory, plot analysis, A Stanford Lit Lab Pamphlet, 2011, <http://litlab.stanford.edu/LiteraryLabPamphlet2A.Text.pdf>.
2. D.J. Watts and S.H. Strogatz, Collective dynamics of “smallworld” networks, Nature, Volume 393, 1998, pages 440–442.
3. A.-L. Barabasi and R. Albert, Emergence of scaling in random networks, Science, Volume 286, 1999, pages 509– 512.
4. A.-L. Barabasi and R. Albert, Statistical mechanics of complex networks, Reviews of Modern Physics 74 (1), 2002, pages 47–97.
5. <http://www.francescobailo.net/apps/the-social-network-of-breaking-bad/>.
6. <http://breakingbad.wikia.com>.
7. A.D. Broido and A. Clauset, Scale-free networks are rare, Nature, 10, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08746-5>.
8. A. Clauset et al., Power-law distributions in empirical data, SIAM Review 51, 2009, pages 661-703, <https://arXiv.org/abs/cond-mat/0706.1062>.
9. M. E. J. Newman, The Mathematics of a Network, <http://www-personal.umich.edu/~mejn/papers/palgrave.pdf> (last seen 01-05-2021).
10. L. Freeman, A set of measures of centrality based upon betweenness, Sociometry, 40, 1977, pages 35–41, [doi:10.2307/3033543](https://doi.org/10.2307/3033543).
11. J. Stiller, D. Nettle and R.I.M. Dunbar, The small world of Shakespeare’s plays, Human Nature, Volume 14, Issue 4, 2003, pages 397-408.
12. A. C. Sparavigna, On social Networks in Plays and Novels, International Journal of Sciences, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.18483/ijSci.312>
13. R. Alberich, J. Miro-Julia and F. Rossello, Marvel Universe looks almost like a real social network, <http://arxiv.org/abs/cond-mat/0202174v1>.
14. Q. K. Telesford et al., The ubiquity of small-world networks, Brain Connectivity, 1, 2011, pages 367–75. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1109.5454>.